

1 **Semi-natural areas act as reservoirs of genetic diversity for crop**
2 **pollinators and natural enemies across Europe**

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4 Joaquín Ortego^{1*}, Matthias Albrecht², András Báldi³, Trine Bilde⁴, Sean Birk Bek Craig⁴, José M.
5 Herrera^{5,6}, Amelia S. C. Hood⁷, David Kleijn⁸, Corina Maurer^{2,9}, Francisco P. Molina¹, Erik
6 Öckinger¹⁰, Simon G. Potts⁷, Virginia Settepani⁴, Philip Francis Thomsen⁴, Marina Trillo¹, Flóra
7 Vajna³, Elena Velado-Alonso¹, and Ignasi Bartomeus^{1*}

8

9 ¹Estación Biológica de Doñana (EBD-CSIC), Seville, Spain

10 ²Agroscope, Agroecology and Environment, Zurich, Switzerland

11 ³Lendület Ecosystem Services Research Group, Institute of Ecology and Botany, HUN-REN
12 Centre for Ecological Research, Vácrátót, Hungary

13 ⁴Department of Biology, Centre for Ecological Genetics, Aarhus University, Denmark

14 ⁵Departamento de Biología, Instituto de Investigación Vitivinícola y Agroalimentaria,
15 Universidad de Cádiz, Puerto Real, Spain

16 ⁶Instituto Mediterrâneo para a Agricultura Ambiente e Desenvolvimento, Universidade de
17 Évora, Évora, Portugal

18 ⁷Centre for Agri-Environmental Research (CAER), School of Agriculture, Policy and
19 Development, Reading University, UK

20 ⁸Plant Ecology and Nature Conservation Group, Wageningen University & Research,
21 Wageningen, The Netherlands

22 ⁹Ecosystems Landscape Evolution, Institute of Terrestrial Ecosystems, Department of
23 Environmental Systems Science, ETH Zürich, Zürich

24 ¹⁰Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Department of Ecology, Uppsala, Sweden

25

26 Authors for correspondence:

27 *Joaquín Ortego, Estación Biológica de Doñana (EBD-CSIC), Avda. Américo Vespucio 26, E-41092
28 Seville, Spain; E-mail: joaquin.ortego@csic.es; Phone: (+34) 955 149 428; Fax: (+34) 954 621 125

29 *Ignasi Bartomeus, Estación Biológica de Doñana (EBD-CSIC), Avda. Américo Vespucio 26, E-
30 41092 Seville, Spain; E-mail: nacho.bartomeus@gmail.com; Phone: (+34) 954 232 340; Fax: (+34)
31 954 621 125

32 **Abstract**

33 Despite increasing recognition of the importance of the multiple dimensions of biodiversity,
34 including functional or genetic diversity as well as species diversity, most conservation studies
35 on ecosystem service-providing insects focus on simple diversity measures such as species
36 richness and abundance. In contrast, relatively little is known about the genetic diversity and
37 resilience of pollinators or natural enemies of crop pests to population fragmentation and local
38 extinction. The genetic diversity and demographic dynamics of remnant populations of
39 beneficial insects in agricultural areas can be a useful indicator providing additional insights into
40 their conservation status, but this is rarely evaluated. Although gene flow between agricultural
41 and semi-natural areas is key to maintaining genetic diversity, its extent and directionality
42 remain largely unexplored. Here, we apply a pan-European sampling protocol to quantify
43 genetic diversity and structure and assess gene flow between agricultural and nearby semi-
44 natural landscapes in populations of two key ecosystem service-providing insect species, the
45 lady beetle *Coccinella septempunctata*, an important predator of aphids and other crop pests,
46 and the bee pollinator *Andrena flavipes*. We show that *A. flavipes* populations are genetically
47 structured at the European level, whereas populations of *C. septempunctata* experience
48 widespread gene flow across the continent and lack any defined genetic structure. In both
49 species, we found that there is high genetic connectivity between populations established in
50 croplands and nearby semi-natural areas and, as a consequence, they harbor similar levels of
51 genetic diversity. Interestingly, demographic models for some regions support asymmetric gene
52 flow from semi-natural areas to nearby agricultural landscapes. Collectively, our study
53 demonstrates how semi-natural areas can serve as genetic reservoirs of both pollinators and
54 natural enemies for nearby agricultural landscapes, acting as sources for recurrent
55 recolonization and, potentially, contributing to enhancing ecosystem service and crop
56 production resilience in the longer term.

57

58 **KEYWORDS** agricultural landscapes, conservation genetics, demography, gene flow, genetic
59 diversity, genetic structure, habitat fragmentation, service-providing insects

60 1. INTRODUCTION

61 With more than 80% of the world's land under the direct influence of agricultural systems,
62 conservation strategies that include agricultural landscapes could potentially be important to
63 buffer and connect protected areas, but also in the direct conservation of species that exist
64 there (Garibaldi et al., 2021; Kleijn et al., 2020). Indeed, protecting those species is becoming
65 particularly important in providing ecosystem services such as enhanced crop yield by
66 pollinators (Klein et al., 2007) and control of pest species by natural enemies (Garratt et al.,
67 2011). Advances have been made in transitioning to lower-intensity agriculture and increasingly
68 adopting an ecological intensification approach (Kleijn et al., 2019), with most efforts focused
69 on halting the loss of species. For example, it has been shown that actions such as planting
70 flower strips can increase pollinator richness and abundance (Scheper et al., 2013), and
71 reduced soil tilling regimes improve the survival and numbers of arthropods in agroecosystems
72 (Thorbeck & Bilde, 2004). However, in addition to restoring and maintaining species diversity, it
73 is necessary to maintain healthy and viable populations, i.e. populations with a sufficient
74 number of individuals to maintain high genetic diversity, which is key to responding to
75 environmental change, and therefore for the long-term persistence of natural populations
76 (Falconer & Mackay, 1996; Frankham, 1995; Spielman et al., 2004). This calls for integrating
77 knowledge of population genetic diversity in the management and conservation of biodiversity
78 (Kardos et al., 2021; Willi et al., 2022).

79 Although it is increasingly acknowledged that it is important to consider multiple
80 dimensions of biodiversity in conservation, most studies to date focus on simple diversity
81 metrics at the level of species, such as richness and abundance (Cerini et al., 2023; Kardos et al.,
82 2021; Willi et al., 2022). Although species diversity metrics have been core for evaluating the
83 effectiveness of conservation and restoration measures, they cannot provide insights into some
84 of the more complex mechanisms underlying biodiversity responses. Biodiversity comprises
85 many levels of organization, from community composition and functional diversity to species
86 metapopulation dynamics and genetic diversity (e.g., United Nations Convention on Biological
87 Diversity; www.cbd.int). In particular, genetic diversity is an often-neglected aspect with far-

88 reaching implications for long-term conservation (Kardos et al., 2021; e.g., Saccheri et al., 1998;
89 Spielman et al., 2004). More genetically diverse populations may better withstand global
90 change pressures, as these populations have a larger genetic pool from which to adapt to new
91 environmental conditions (Frankham et al., 2005; Kardos et al., 2021). However, the impact of
92 land-use changes on the genetic diversity of arthropods and the connectivity between
93 populations from semi-natural and agricultural landscapes in insect species that provide
94 important ecosystem functions and services are still poorly known (González et al., 2020;
95 Keyghobadi, 2007; Schlaepfer et al., 2018; Webster et al., 2023).

96 Insects and other arthropods providing ecosystem services are often highly mobile
97 organisms that disperse and forage across habitats in heterogeneous landscapes (e.g., Jaffé et
98 al., 2016; Lecompte et al., 2016). This implies that their persistence and conservation does not
99 only rely on local habitat quality but also on the landscape-level habitat composition and
100 configuration, in particular, connectivity between suitable habitats (Kremen et al., 2007; Martin
101 et al., 2019). A generally observed pattern is that croplands surrounded by a larger proportion
102 of natural habitats tend to support relatively higher beneficial insect diversity and abundance,
103 which facilitates ecosystem services such as pollination and pest control (Dainese et al. 2019).
104 However, most insect conservation studies focus on a single habitat type (either agricultural or
105 semi-natural habitats), and rarely integrate different habitats within the same landscape
106 (Marini et al., 2019). In fact, our understanding of how source-sink metapopulation dynamics
107 work in agricultural systems is still very limited (e.g., Ballare & Jha, 2021; Dreier et al., 2014; Jha,
108 2015; Ortego et al., 2015a). Many species are able to maintain sustainable populations in
109 agricultural habitats, but other species may not be able to persist in simplified agricultural
110 habitats without continuous immigration from nearby natural or semi-natural areas, i.e. the
111 agricultural habitats acts as population sinks and the (semi-)natural areas as population sources
112 (e.g., Öckinger & Smith, 2007a, b). Either way, the benefits of having bidirectional gene flow
113 between natural and agricultural areas can be important, even when populations would be able
114 to persist in isolation; for example, this would promote long-term persistence of species if one
115 area is subject to a major disturbance, as the remaining populations in neighboring habitats can
116 repopulate and contribute to gene flow towards the disturbed area. However, in what way

117 natural areas contribute to the genetic diversity of ecosystem service providing insect
118 populations in nearby agricultural landscapes and *vice versa* has, to our knowledge, not yet
119 been explored (Webster et al., 2023).

120 To improve our understanding of the importance of natural habitats for the
121 conservation of population genetic diversity of key ecosystem service-providing insects, we
122 used a pan-European sampling design to characterize gene flow dynamics between populations
123 of the pest control agent *Coccinella septempunctata* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) and the bee
124 pollinator *Andrena flavipes* (Hymenoptera: Andrenidae) in agricultural areas and nearby semi-
125 natural landscapes. These are two of the most common ecosystem service providers in Europe,
126 with *A. flavipes* ranking 7th in a recent review of the most common bee crop pollinators in
127 Europe (Kleijn et al., 2015) whereas *C. septempunctata* is a widespread predator of aphids
128 (Jervis & Kidd, 1996; New, 1991), a ubiquitous pest of several crops. To this end, we sampled
129 and genotyped populations of the two focal species in agricultural and nearby semi-natural
130 areas across Europe (i.e., a paired-replicated approach), quantified their respective levels of
131 population genetic diversity and structure, and tested alternative models of gene flow.
132 Specifically, we first (i) tested the hypothesis that populations in semi-natural areas sustain
133 larger effective population sizes and, thus, present higher levels of genetic diversity, than those
134 established in agricultural landscapes. We then quantified spatial patterns of genetic structure
135 across the different European regions, and (ii) tested the hypothesis that populations of mobile
136 beneficial insects from semi-natural and agricultural landscapes regularly exchange gene flow
137 and show limited genetic structure (e.g., Jaffé et al. 2016; Lecompte et al., 2016). Finally, we
138 used a coalescent-based model-testing approach to evaluate alternative demographic scenarios
139 and (iii) test the hypothesis that semi-natural areas play a role as sources of gene flow for
140 populations established in agricultural landscapes (Figure 1). Our study demonstrates how
141 semi-natural areas can serve as genetic reservoirs of both pollinators and natural enemies for
142 nearby agricultural landscapes, acting as sources for recurrent recolonization and, potentially,
143 contributing to enhance ecosystem services and crop production resilience in the longer term.
144 These results, general across a network of European sites, directly appeal to practitioners and
145 policy makers – e.g., through the European Union's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) – and

146 emphasize the importance of implementing management actions aimed at preserving or
147 restoring semi-natural habitats for the maintenance of source populations of ecosystem
148 service-providing insects in agricultural landscapes.

149

150 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

151 **2.1. Population sampling**

152 In spring and summer 2021, we sampled pairs of populations of *Coccinella septempunctata* and
153 *Andrena flavipes* in agricultural landscapes (i.e., dominated by agriculturally managed land for
154 the last 100 years) and nearby semi-natural areas (i.e., dominated by semi-natural habitat that
155 was not under agricultural management at least in the last 100 years) separated by <25 km
156 (mean: 11.9 km; range: 4.6-24.0 km; Table 1; Figure 2 and Figure S1). The selected species are
157 representative of generalist ecosystem service providers within their guild, and are often locally
158 abundant and widely distributed. In semi-natural areas, specimens were collected in patches of
159 native vegetation, whereas specimens from agricultural areas were collected within crop fields
160 and along paths and field margins. We targeted to sample 8-10 specimens per species and site
161 area and aimed to replicate this sampling scheme in seven European countries: Estonia,
162 Denmark, Netherlands, Great Britain, Hungary, Switzerland, and Spain (Figure 2 and Figure S1).
163 However, low population densities in some areas often reduced our sample sizes and one of
164 the two focal taxa could not be collected in some countries at a minimum sample size of $n = 5$ in
165 agricultural and/or semi-natural sites (Table 1). Consequently, our sampling scheme could be
166 replicated in six countries for *C. septempunctata* and four countries for *A. flavipes* and final
167 datasets included 5-10 genotyped specimens per species, country, and area (mean = 8; mode =
168 8; Table 1). Our pan-European sampling scheme, and the countries selected for our study,
169 frames within the context of a multi-partner project funded by the European Union's Horizon
170 2020 Research and Innovation Programme H2020. We spread the sampling across each site
171 (<500 m of radius around sampling coordinates; Table 1) to avoid collecting closely related
172 individuals (i.e., siblings or half-siblings). Specimens were collected by hand (C.

173 *septempunctata*) or sweep-netting (*A. flavipes*) and preserved at -20 °C in 1500 µL ethanol 96%
174 until DNA extraction. We registered spatial coordinates of each sampling plot using a Global
175 Positioning System (GPS). Further details on sampling locations are provided in Table 1.

176

177 **2.2. Genomic library preparation and processing**

178 We extracted and purified DNA from each specimen using NucleoSpin Tissue kits (Macherey-
179 Nagel, Düren, Germany). We processed genomic DNA into different genomic libraries using the
180 double-digestion restriction-fragment-based procedure (ddRAD-seq) described in Peterson et
181 al. (2012). In brief, we digested DNA with the restriction enzymes MseI and EcoRI (New England
182 Biolabs, Ipswich, MA, USA) and ligated Illumina adaptors including unique 7-bp barcodes to the
183 digested fragments of each individual. We pooled ligation products, size-selected them
184 between 350-450 bp with a Pippin Prep machine (Sage Science, Beverly, MA, USA), and
185 amplified the fragments by PCR with 12 cycles using the iProof™ High-Fidelity DNA
186 Polymerase (BIO-RAD, Veenendaal, The Netherlands). Single-read 201-bp sequencing was
187 performed on an Illumina NovaSeq6000 platform. We used the different programs distributed
188 as part of the STACKS v. 1.35 pipeline (Catchen et al., 2013) to filter and assemble our sequences
189 into *de novo* loci, call genotypes, calculate genetic diversity statistics, and export input files for
190 all downstream analyses (Methods S1). Unless otherwise indicated, all downstream analyses
191 were performed using datasets including only the first single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)
192 per RAD locus (180-bp length, see Methods S1) and retaining loci with a minimum stack depth \geq
193 5 ($m = 5$) and that were represented in at least 75% of the populations ($p = 9$ for *C.*
194 *septempunctata* and $p = 6$ for *A. flavipes*) and 50% of the individuals within each population ($r =$
195 0.5).

196

197 **2.3. Quantifying genetic structure**

198 We calculated genetic differentiation between each pair of populations using the Weir &
199 Cockerham weighted fixation index (F_{ST}) (Weir & Cockerham, 1984) as implemented in ARLEQUIN
200 v. 3.5 (Excoffier & Lischer, 2010). We determined statistical significance with Fisher's exact tests

201 after 10,000 permutations, applying a false discovery rate (FDR) adjustment (5%, $q < 0.05$) to
202 control for multiple tests. We performed Mantel tests to analyze the association between
203 genetic differentiation (F_{ST}) and geographical distances among populations of each focal species
204 using ZT software with 10,000 permutations (Bonnet & Van de Peer, 2002). We quantified
205 population genetic structure and admixture using the Bayesian Markov chain Monte Carlo
206 clustering method implemented in the program STRUCTURE v. 2.3.3 (Pritchard et al., 2000). We
207 conducted STRUCTURE analyses hierarchically, initially analyzing data from all populations of each
208 taxon jointly and, subsequently, running independent analyses for subsets of populations
209 assigned to the same genetic cluster in the previous hierarchical level analysis (e.g., González-
210 Serna et al., 2019). To make analyses computationally tractable, we ran STRUCTURE using a
211 random subset of 10,000 SNPs. We ran STRUCTURE analyses assuming correlated allele
212 frequencies and admixture and without using prior population information (Hubisz et al., 2009).
213 We conducted 15 independent runs for each value of K (from $K = 1$ to $K = 10$) to estimate the
214 most likely number of genetic clusters with 200,000 MCMC cycles, following a burn-in step of
215 100,000 iterations. We retained the ten runs having the highest likelihood for each value of K
216 and determined the number of genetic clusters that best describes our data according to log
217 probabilities of the data ($\ln Pr(X|K)$) (Pritchard et al., 2000) and the ΔK method (Evanno et al.,
218 2005), as implemented in STRUCTURE HARVESTER (Earl & vonHoldt, 2012). We used CLUMPP v. 1.1.2
219 and the Greedy algorithm to align multiple runs of STRUCTURE for the same K value (Jakobsson &
220 Rosenberg, 2007) and DISTRUCT v. 1.1 (Rosenberg, 2004) to visualize the individuals' probabilities
221 of population membership in bar plots. Complementarily, we used the same datasets of 10,000
222 random SNPs to perform principal component analyses (PCA) as implemented in the R v. 4.2.1
223 (R Core Team, 2022) package 'adeget' (Jombart, 2008). Before running PCAs, we replaced
224 missing data by the mean allele frequency of the corresponding locus estimated across all
225 samples (Jombart, 2008). Results from PCAs were visualized using the R package 'scatterplot3d'
226 (Ligges & Mächler, 2003).

227 **2.4. Testing alternative models of gene flow**

228 We used the simulation-based approach implemented in FASTSIMCOAL2 to evaluate alternative
229 migration models and test the hypothesis of asymmetric gene flow between populations from
230 agricultural landscapes and nearby semi-natural areas (Excoffier et al., 2013; Figure 1a).
231 Specifically, we tested four alternative migration models for each taxon (*C. septempunctata* and
232 *A. flavipes*) and spatial replicate (i.e., country), including a null-model considering no gene flow
233 between populations from agricultural and semi-natural areas (Model A), a model of symmetric
234 gene flow (Model B), and two models of unidirectional gene flow, one fitting unidirectional
235 gene flow from agricultural to semi-natural areas (Model C) and another exclusively considering
236 unidirectional gene flow in the opposite direction (Model D) (Figure 1b). We used the site
237 frequency spectrum (SFS) and FASTSIMCOAL2 to estimate the composite likelihood of the
238 observed data given a specified model (Excoffier et al., 2013). For each taxon and pair of
239 populations, we calculated a folded joint SFS considering a single SNP per locus. Because we did
240 not include invariable sites in the SFS, we fixed the contemporary effective population size for
241 one of the demes (ϑ_{AGR} in all cases; see Figure 1b) to enable the estimation of other parameters
242 in FASTSIMCOAL2 (Excoffier et al., 2013). The effective population size fixed in the model was
243 calculated from the level of nucleotide diversity (π) and estimates of mutation rates per site per
244 generation (μ). Nucleotide diversity (π) was estimated from polymorphic and non-polymorphic
245 loci using STACKS (Table 1). We used the mutation rate per site per generation (2.8×10^{-9})
246 estimated for *Drosophila melanogaster* (Keightley et al., 2014), which is similar to the
247 spontaneous mutation rate estimated for the butterfly *Heliconius melpomene* (2.9×10^{-9} ;
248 Keightley et al., 2015). To remove all missing data for the calculation of the SFS, minimize errors
249 with allele frequency estimates, and maximize the number of retained SNPs, each population
250 group was downsampled using a Python script written by Qixin He and available on Dryad
251 (Papadopoulou & Knowles, 2015). Note that this downsampling procedure necessarily results in
252 the number of SNPs retained in the SFS differ across each pair of analyzed populations, as this
253 depends on the number of available samples and the pattern and amount of missing data in
254 each specific dataset (Table 2; e.g., Papadopoulou & Knowles, 2015).

255 Each model was run 100 independent times considering 100,000-250,000 simulations
256 for the calculation of the composite likelihood, 10-40 expectation-conditional maximization

257 (ECM) cycles, and a stopping criterion of 0.001 (Excoffier & Foll, 2011; Excoffier et al., 2013). We
258 used an information-theoretic model selection approach based on the Akaike's information
259 criterion (AIC) to compare the set of candidate models and identify the one that is best
260 supported by the data (Burnham & Anderson, 2002; e.g., Ortego et al., 2021; Thome &
261 Carsterns, 2016). After the maximum likelihood was estimated for each model in every
262 replicate, we calculated the AIC scores as detailed in Thome & Carsterns (2016). AIC values for
263 each model were rescaled (ΔAIC), calculating the difference between the AIC value of each
264 model and the minimum AIC obtained among all competing models (i.e., the best model has
265 $\Delta AIC = 0$). Point estimates of the different demographic parameters for the best supported
266 model were selected from the run with the highest maximum composite likelihood. Finally, we
267 calculated confidence intervals of parameter estimates (based on the percentile method; e.g.,
268 de Manuel et al., 2016) from 100 parametric bootstrap replicates by simulating SFS from the
269 maximum composite likelihood estimates and re-estimating parameters each time (Excoffier et
270 al., 2013).

271 **3. RESULTS**

272 **3.1. Samples and genomic data**

273 Overall, we obtained samples of *C. septempunctata* and *A. flavipes* from six and four countries,
274 respectively, with three countries sampling both species (Table 1). The average number of
275 reads retained per individual after the different quality filtering steps was 3,409,688 (range =
276 236,373-9,557,006 reads) for *C. septempunctata* (Figure S2) and 2,103,765 (range = 420,468-
277 6,255,835 reads) for *A. flavipes* (Figure S3). On average, this represented 86% (range = 64-90%)
278 and 73% (range = 60-81%) of the total number of reads recovered for each individual of *C.*
279 *septempunctata* and *A. flavipes*, respectively. After filtering loci (see Methods S1), the final
280 dataset including all genotyped populations of *C. septempunctata* contained 10,896 SNPs, with
281 a mean coverage depth of 25 \times (mode = 35 \times ; range = 12-42 \times) and an average proportion of
282 missing data of 23% (mode = 10%; range = 0-77%). For *A. flavipes*, the final dataset contained

283 18,554 SNPs, with a mean coverage depth of 25× (mode = 26×; range = 7-39×) and an average
284 proportion of missing data of 27% (mode = 24%; range = 17-77%).

285 **3.2. Genetic diversity of populations**

286 Levels of genetic diversity in populations of *C. septempunctata* and *A. flavipes* are presented in
287 Table 1. In *C. septempunctata*, individual genetic diversity (i.e., observed heterozygosity) did
288 not significantly differ among populations sampled in different countries (one-way ANOVA: $F_{5,96}$
289 = 0.99, $p = 0.423$) or between populations from agricultural landscapes and nearby semi-natural
290 areas within any of the countries (all p -values > 0.3). In *A. flavipes*, individual genetic diversity
291 significantly differed among populations sampled in different countries (one-way ANOVA: $F_{3,56} =$
292 5.85, $p = 0.002$) and post hoc Tukey's tests revealed that such differences resulted from
293 comparisons involving populations from Denmark, which showed lower levels of genetic
294 diversity than populations from the other countries ($p < 0.06$ in all cases; Table 1). As in *C.*
295 *septempunctata*, individual genetic diversity did not significantly differ between populations of
296 *A. flavipes* from agricultural landscapes and nearby semi-natural areas within countries (all p -
297 values > 0.3).

298 **3.3. Quantifying genetic structure**

299 In *C. septempunctata*, all pairwise F_{ST} values were non-significantly different from zero (Table
300 S1). In contrast, pairwise F_{ST} values in *A. flavipes* ranged between 0 and 0.444 and several pairs
301 of populations showed significant genetic differentiation (Table S2). Except for comparisons
302 involving populations from the Netherlands and Switzerland, all pairs of populations of *A.*
303 *flavipes* from different countries were significantly differentiated (Table S2). Within most
304 countries, populations of *A. flavipes* from agricultural landscapes and nearby semi-natural areas
305 did not show significant genetic differentiation (Table S2). The only exception was the
306 comparison involving the two populations from Denmark, albeit with a small F_{ST} value ($F_{ST} =$
307 0.03; Table S2). Simple Mantel tests revealed that genetic differentiation (F_{ST}) is positively
308 correlated with geographical distances among populations in *A. flavipes* ($r = 0.96$, $p < 0.001$, $n =$
309 8) but not in *C. septempunctata* ($r = 0.00$, $p = 1.000$, $n = 12$). STRUCTURE analyses for *C.*

310 *septempunctata* showed that $\text{LnPr}(X|K)$ peaked at $K = 2$ and decreased for higher K -values
311 (Figure S4a). For $K = 2$, all individuals and populations of *C. septempunctata* presented a very
312 low probability of assignment ($q < 0.05$) to one of the two genetic clusters (i.e., a “fictive” or
313 “ghost” cluster *sensu* Guillot et al., 2005; see also Chen et al., 2007), which indicates a lack of
314 genetic structure across analyzed populations of this taxon (Figure 3a). Clustering solutions for
315 higher K -values (from $K = 3$ to $K = 5$) did not reveal either any genetic structure in *C.*
316 *septempunctata* (Figure S5a). STRUCTURE analyses for *A. flavipes* considering all populations
317 identified the most likely number of clusters as $K = 2$ according to the ΔK criterion and
318 $\text{LnPr}(X|K)$ reached a plateau at the same K value (Figure S4b). For $K = 2$, the two genetic clusters
319 separated the populations of *A. flavipes* from Spain from the rest of European populations
320 (Figure 3b). STRUCTURE analyses at a lower hierarchical level, and excluding Spanish populations,
321 identified the most likely number of clusters as $K = 2$ according to the ΔK criterion and
322 $\text{LnPr}(X|K)$ reached a plateau at the same K value (Figure S4c). In this case, the two genetic
323 clusters separated the populations from Denmark from the populations from the Netherlands
324 and Switzerland, which grouped together (Figure 3b). The new genetic clusters that arise for
325 higher K -values (from $K = 3$ to $K = 5$) were either similarly represented in all populations of *A.*
326 *flavipes* assigned to the same genetic cluster for $K = 2$ or were circumscribed to certain
327 populations but showed very low probabilities assignment in all individuals ($q < 0.15$; Figure
328 S5b, c). Principal component analyses (PCA) confirmed the results yielded by STRUCTURE for the
329 two taxa (Figure 4). For *C. septempunctata*, PCA did not reveal any genetic clustering and
330 individuals collected in different countries and sites were interspersed across the three first
331 principal components (Figure 4a). For *A. flavipes*, PCA separated Spanish populations from the
332 rest of European populations along the first principal component (PC1) (Figure 4b, c). The
333 second principal component (PC2) separated the populations from Denmark from those
334 sampled in the Netherlands and Switzerland, which also tended to segregate along the third
335 principal component (PC3) (Figure 4b). Analyses for *A. flavipes* excluding Spanish populations
336 provided similar results, with PC1 separating populations from Denmark from those sampled in
337 the Netherlands and Switzerland, which in this case tended to segregate along PC2 (Figure 4c).

338

339 3.4. Testing alternative models of gene flow

340 Demographic analyses in FASTSIMCOAL2 supported unidirectional gene flow from populations in
341 semi-natural areas to those in agricultural landscapes (Model D; Figure 1b) in five out of six *C.*
342 *sempunctata* (EE, DK, NL, HU and CH) and two out of four *A. flavipes* (NL, ES) pairwise
343 comparisons (Table 2). In the rest of the comparisons (*C. sempunctata* in GB and *A. flavipes*
344 in DK and CH), the best supported model was a scenario of unidirectional gene flow from
345 populations in agricultural landscapes to those in nearby semi-natural areas (Model C; Table 2).
346 In the case of populations of *C. sempunctata* from Great Britain (GB), the second-best
347 supported model (Model D) was statistically indistinguishable from the best supported model
348 (Model C) ($\Delta AIC = 0.79$), indicating that the two alternative models of unidirectional gene flow
349 are similarly probable (Table 2). Estimates of migration rates between populations were fairly
350 similar across all pairwise comparisons, ranging from 2.35×10^{-4} to 5.79×10^{-4} in *C.*
351 *sempunctata* and from 2.27×10^{-4} to 5.67×10^{-4} in *A. flavipes* (Table 3). In both *C.*
352 *sempunctata* and *A. flavipes*, estimates of gene flow from populations established in
353 agricultural areas to those in nearby semi-natural areas (i.e., Model C) were smaller than
354 estimates obtained when the most supported model was the scenario of unidirectional gene
355 flow in the opposite direction (i.e., Model D) (Table 3).

356

357 4. DISCUSSION

358 Our data support contrasting patterns of genetic structure and gene flow in two key ecosystem
359 service providing insect species, the natural enemy *C. sempunctata* and the pollinator *A.*
360 *flavipes*. A panmictic structure characterizes populations of *C. sempunctata* across both local
361 and regional scales. Conversely, populations of *A. flavipes* present a marked structure at a
362 European scale, but a very limited or null genetic differentiation between nearby agricultural
363 and semi-natural landscapes within each country. We found no support for the hypothesis of
364 higher levels of genetic diversity in populations from semi-natural areas with respect to those
365 established in agricultural landscapes. However, demographic model testing and coalescent-
366 based estimates of migration rates lent partial support to the hypothesis of increased gene flow

367 from semi-natural to agricultural landscapes (Figure 1a). For *C. septempunctata*, models
368 considering anisotropic gene flow in the predicted direction received comparatively higher
369 statistical support than the rest of the scenarios across most landscape replicates (i.e.,
370 countries), while the evidence on this respect for *A. flavipes* was limited to 50% of the regions.
371 Collectively, these results emphasize the occurrence of gene flow from semi-natural to
372 cultivated areas and confirm the importance of preserving semi-natural habitats at the
373 landscape level for the maintenance of source populations of ecosystem service-providing
374 insects (Garibaldi et al., 2021).

375

376 **4.1. Genetic diversity and structure at regional and landscape scales**

377 Analyses of genetic differentiation (F_{ST}) and structure (STRUCTURE and PCAs) revealed marked
378 differences in the spatial distribution of genomic variation in the two focal taxa (Figures 3-4).
379 Populations of *C. septempunctata* were panmictic and presented no evidence for genetic
380 differentiation at both European and landscape scales, a phenomenon likely explained by the
381 long-distance migratory behavior linked to seasonal aggregations characterizing many
382 coccinellids (Hagen, 1962). Long-distance dispersal in this taxon is exemplified by unrestricted
383 gene flow between British and mainland European populations, which indicates the limited
384 effects of seawater as a barrier to dispersal (i.e., The English Channel is 34 km at its narrowest).
385 These results are in line with the findings of a previous microsatellite-based study covering the
386 entire distribution of the species (Lecompte et al., 2016). This study revealed a lack of genetic
387 structure, very limited differentiation ($F_{ST} < 0.05$), and a weak pattern of isolation-by-distance
388 across populations sampled from Portugal to India. Only eastern Asia (China, Japan) and some
389 North African populations (Algeria) were assigned to different genetic clusters and presented a
390 significant genetic differentiation ($F_{ST} = 0.10-0.30$), which suggests either long-term isolation of
391 these peripheral populations (e.g., in different glacial refugia) or the evolution of reproductive
392 isolation and an incipient process of cryptic speciation (Lecompte et al., 2016).

393 In contrast, analyses for *A. flavipes* revealed a marked genetic structure and
394 differentiation ($F_{ST} = 0.10-0.44$) at a European scale, with more peripheral populations from
395 Jutland (DK) and Iberian (ES) peninsulas forming distinct genetic clusters with limited gene flow
396 between them as well as with the rest of analyzed populations (Figures 3-4). Likewise, although
397 central European populations from NL and CH (separated by >400 km) clustered together in
398 STRUCTURE analyses (Figure 2 and S5) and showed non-significant genetic differentiation ($F_{ST} = 0$;
399 Table S2), they tended to segregate in PCAs (Figure 4). These results reveal more limited gene
400 flow in *A. flavipes* than in *C. septempunctata* at a continental scale, which has likely resulted in
401 the development of genetic structure across populations from most studied regions. In
402 contrast, populations from agricultural and nearby semi-natural landscapes within countries
403 presented weak genetic differentiation in *A. flavipes* ($F_{ST} < 0.03$). Only the two sites within
404 Denmark showed significant differentiation, albeit with a very low estimate ($F_{ST} = 0.03$).
405 Remarkably, populations of *A. flavipes* from Denmark showed the lowest levels of genetic
406 diversity compared to the rest of European populations, which suggests that demographic
407 stochasticity, founder effects, genetic drift and low effective population sizes characterizing
408 leading-edge peripheral populations could have contributed to fine spatial-scale (<5 km)
409 genetic structure between populations from agricultural and nearby semi-natural landscapes
410 within Jutland Peninsula (Hampe & Petit, 2005; Lira-Noriega & Manthey, 2014). Weak genetic
411 structure at local and landscape spatial scales has been previously reported in other
412 Andrenidae (e.g., *Andrena fuscipes*: Exeler et al., 2010; *Andrena vaga*: Černá et al., 2013; Exeler
413 et al., 2008), bumblebees (e.g., *Bombus terrestris*; Silva et al., 2020), stingless bees (e.g.,
414 *Trigona spinipes*; Jaffé et al., 2016), and carpenter bees (e.g., *Xylocopa virginica*; Ballare & Jha,
415 2021).

416 Collectively, these results are in line with the findings of spatially-explicit landscape
417 genetic studies suggesting a limited impact of habitat fragmentation and structure on the
418 distribution of spatial patterns of genetic variation in different pollinators (Barbosa et al., 2022;
419 Exeler et al., 2010; Jackson et al., 2018; Jha & Kremen, 2013). Aligned with inferences from
420 analyses of genetic structure, testing of alternative demographic models strongly rejected the
421 scenario of strict isolation (i.e., total lack of gene flow; Model A) between populations from

422 agricultural and natural areas in the two focal taxa (Table 2). Connectivity between nearby
423 areas of different land use is expected to contribute to prevent genetic drift and loss of genetic
424 diversity through time, which can explain similar levels of genetic variation across populations
425 from natural and agricultural landscapes (Table 1).

426

427 **4.2. Anisotropic gene flow between agricultural and semi-natural landscapes**

428 Asymmetric gene flow has been previously documented linked to passive dispersal in the
429 direction of prevailing winds or ocean currents (e.g., Bertola et al., 2020; Kling & Ackerly, 2021)
430 and associated to differences in the production of propagules in the context of central-
431 peripheral and source-sink metapopulation dynamics (Kirkpatrick & Barton, 1997; e.g., Hauser
432 et al., 2019; Holliday et al., 2012). Our model-based approach provided mixed support to the
433 hypothesis of directional gene flow from populations in semi-natural areas to those sustained in
434 nearby agricultural landscapes (Figure 1). Coalescent-based model testing in the natural enemy
435 *C. septempunctata* largely supported unidirectional gene flow in the predicted direction (Model
436 D), suggesting that semi-natural areas genetically subsidize conspecific populations established
437 in nearby croplands. These results are in line with previous capture-mark-recapture and
438 observational studies pointing to the role of semi-natural landscapes as population sources for
439 beneficial insects (Öckinger & Smith, 2007a, b). Although analyses in *A. flavipes* consistently
440 supported models fitting asymmetric migration rates over those considering symmetric gene
441 exchange, the scenario of unidirectional gene flow from semi-natural to agricultural landscapes
442 was the most supported one in only half of our spatial replicates. Remarkably, the bidirectional
443 migration model received low statistical support in all spatial replicates for both *C.*
444 *septempunctata* and *A. flavipes*, suggesting that asymmetric gene flow and source-sink
445 dynamics govern the demography of the focal taxa in natural-agricultural mosaic landscapes
446 (Hanski, 1998). Under this scenario, source populations with a net growth supply individuals to
447 sink populations, reducing the chances of extinction of small populations and contributing to
448 increasing the stability and maintaining the levels of genetic diversity of the whole
449 metapopulation (Howe et al., 1991; e.g., Ortego et al., 2008; Saccheri et al., 1998). It must be

450 noted, however, that source-sink dynamics in highly anthropized landscapes are only expected
451 to be established among generalist taxa with relatively high dispersal ability (e.g., Keller et al.,
452 2013; Ortego et al., 2015b), such as the two widespread ecosystem service-providing species
453 analyzed in our study (Jervis & Kidd, 1996; Kleijn et al., 2015; New, 1991). Rare species with
454 more limited dispersal or increased sensitivity to population subdivision (e.g., pools of
455 regionally threatened species) will likely experience dispersal depression, population isolation,
456 reduced levels of genetic diversity, and increased chances of local extinction under the severe
457 fragmentation of natural habitats that characterize most agricultural landscapes (e.g., Jauker et
458 al., 2009; Ortego et al., 2015a; Schtickzelle et al., 2006).

459

460 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

461 Collectively, our results support high genetic connectivity between populations established in
462 agricultural and nearby semi-natural landscapes, indicating that i) the latter may serve – at least
463 in some cases – as reservoirs of both natural enemies and pollinators for surrounding
464 agricultural areas, ii) act as sources for recurrent recolonization, and iii) potentially contribute
465 to enhance ecosystem services and crop production. This highlights the importance of
466 conserving complex agricultural systems which embed semi-natural areas within productive
467 regions, as those can boost gene flow exchange and contribute to demographic reinforcement
468 of populations of ecosystem service-providing insects and increase the chances that they
469 persist and maintain their important functional role through time.

470

471 **AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS**

472 JO and IB designed the study. IB coordinated the study. MA, AB, TB, SBBC, JMH, AH, DK, CM,
473 FPM, EO, SGP, VS, PFT, FV, EV-A, and IB collected the samples. MT performed the lab work
474 supervised by JO. JO analyzed the data. JO and IB drafted the manuscript. All authors revised
475 the manuscript and contributed to writing.

476

477 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

478 We thank Claus Rasmussen for help with the identification of sampling sites and bee species
479 recognition in Denmark, Zsolt Józán for identification of bees from Hungary, Roel d’Haese and
480 Carmen Näf for their help with the insect sampling in Switzerland, Gabriella Bishop and Reinier
481 de Vries for field assistance in the Netherlands, Natural England and the National Trust for
482 permission to sample on Studland and Godlingston Heaths, and Lulworth Estate for permission
483 to sample on their land. We also thank two anonymous referees for their constructive and
484 valuable comments on an earlier version of the manuscript. Logistic support was provided by
485 Laboratorio de Ecología Molecular (LEM-EBD) from Estación Biológica de Doñana (CSIC). We
486 also thank Centro de Supercomputación de Galicia (CESGA) and Doñana's Singular Scientific-
487 Technical Infrastructure (ICTS-RBD) for access to computer resources. This study was funded by
488 the project SHOWCASE (SHOWCASing synergies between agriculture, biodiversity, and
489 ecosystem services to help farmers capitalizing on native biodiversity) within the European
490 Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (grant agreement No. 862480), and
491 by Programa QUALIFICA, Junta de Andalucía, Consejería de Universidad, Investigación e
492 Innovación (project QUAL21020EBD). The collection of samples in Denmark was funded by the
493 Novo Nordisk Challenge Programme (grant NNF20OC0060118).

494

495 **CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT**

496 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

497

498 **DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT**

499 Raw Illumina reads have been deposited at the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under
500 BioProject PRJNA1036856. Input files for all analyses (STRUCTURE, PCA, ARLEQUIN, and
501 FASTSIMCOAL2) are available for download from Figshare
502 (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24525019>).

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504 **ORCID**

505 Joaquín Ortego <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2709-429X>
506 Ignasi Bartomeus <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7893-4389>
507 András Báldi <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6063-3721>
508 Amelia Hood <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3803-0603>
509 Flóra Vajna <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4451-855X>

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753

754 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

755

756 Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at
757 the end of this article.

758 **TABLE 1** Geographical location, number of genotyped individuals (n), and genetic diversity statistics (π , H_O , and H_E) for populations of
759 *Coccinella septempunctata* and *Andrena flavipes* sampled in agricultural and nearby semi-natural landscapes. Genetic diversity
760 statistics were calculated in STACKS for all positions (polymorphic and non-polymorphic) and only variant (polymorphic) positions.
761 Average values across loci are presented for nucleotide diversity (π), and observed (H_O) and expected (H_E) heterozygosity.

Country	Code	Site	Latitude	Longitude	n	All positions			Variant positions		
						π	H_O	H_E	π	H_O	H_E
<i>(a) Coccinella septempunctata</i>											
Estonia	EE	Agricultural	58.82436	23.59144	10	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0541	0.0299	0.0504
Estonia	EE	Semi-natural	58.79168	23.51234	8	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0537	0.0298	0.0489
Denmark	DK	Agricultural	56.29121	10.40226	8	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0539	0.0318	0.0489
Denmark	DK	Semi-natural	56.28052	10.46685	10	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0551	0.0310	0.0514
Netherlands	NL	Agricultural	50.79752	5.79459	8	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0564	0.0309	0.0517
Netherlands	NL	Semi-natural	50.82924	5.87514	8	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0546	0.0311	0.0497
Great Britain	GB	Agricultural	50.65034	-2.28968	8	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0527	0.0288	0.0482
Great Britain	GB	Semi-natural	50.64681	-2.00065	8	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0557	0.0308	0.0509
Hungary	HU	Agricultural	46.93410	19.10340	8	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0541	0.0297	0.0495
Hungary	HU	Semi-natural	47.11210	19.28140	10	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0565	0.0309	0.0526
Switzerland	CH	Agricultural	47.06575	7.24068	8	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0532	0.0326	0.0486
Switzerland	CH	Semi-natural	47.19120	7.31626	8	0.0003	0.0002	0.0003	0.0541	0.0308	0.0493
<i>(b) Andrena flavipes</i>											
Denmark	DK	Agricultural	56.29121	10.40226	8	0.0003	0.0003	0.0003	0.0608	0.0493	0.0558
Denmark	DK	Semi-natural	56.27405	10.46778	6	0.0003	0.0003	0.0003	0.0555	0.0482	0.0505
Netherlands	NL	Agricultural	50.79752	5.79459	8	0.0004	0.0003	0.0004	0.0711	0.0557	0.0654
Netherlands	NL	Semi-natural	50.82924	5.87514	7	0.0004	0.0003	0.0004	0.0738	0.0599	0.0672
Switzerland	CH	Agricultural	47.06575	7.24068	8	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004	0.0771	0.0652	0.0710
Switzerland	CH	Semi-natural	47.02291	7.31958	8	0.0004	0.0003	0.0004	0.0777	0.0625	0.0716
Spain	ES	Agricultural	37.32987	-6.19802	10	0.0004	0.0003	0.0004	0.0800	0.0572	0.0747
Spain	ES	Semi-natural	37.23660	-6.18450	5	0.0004	0.0003	0.0004	0.0766	0.0561	0.0662

762

763 **TABLE 2** Alternative demographic models (detailed in Figure 1b) tested using FASTSIMCOAL2 for
 764 pairs of populations of *Coccinella septempunctata* and *Andrena flavipes* sampled in agricultural
 765 and nearby semi-natural landscapes from different countries. Best-supported scenarios are
 766 highlighted in bold. The number of variable single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) retained to
 767 calculate the site frequency spectrum is indicated in parentheses. Population codes as
 768 described in Table 1.

769

Model	lnL	k	AIC	ΔAIC	ω _i	lnL	k	AIC	ΔAIC	ω _i
(a) <i>Coccinella septempunctata</i>										
Estonia (EE) (3860 SNPs)						Denmark (DK) (5127 SNPs)				
A	-4405.22	3	8816.44	108.65	0.00	-5498.61	3	11,003.21	156.03	0.00
B	-4354.34	4	8716.67	8.88	0.01	-5423.18	4	10,854.36	7.17	0.03
C	-4352.98	4	8713.97	6.17	0.04	-5425.60	4	10,859.20	12.01	0.00
D	-4349.90	4	8707.79	0.00	0.95	-5419.59	4	10,847.18	0.00	0.97
Netherlands (NL) (2586 SNPs)						Great Britain (GB) (2933 SNPs)				
A	-2852.51	3	5711.03	79.03	0.00	-3263.30	3	6532.60	47.78	0.00
B	-2813.05	4	5634.09	2.10	0.21	-3239.54	4	6487.07	2.25	0.16
C	-2813.02	4	5634.05	2.05	0.21	-3238.41	4	6484.82	0.00	0.50
D	-2812.00	4	5631.99	0.00	0.59	-3238.81	4	6485.62	0.79	0.34
Hungary (HU) (5822 SNPs)						Switzerland (CH) (2769 SNPs)				
A	-6373.50	3	12,753.00	170.70	0.00	-3046.27	3	6098.53	51.44	0.00
B	-6291.05	4	12,590.09	7.78	0.02	-3021.12	4	6050.24	3.15	0.15
C	-6289.01	4	12,586.01	3.70	0.13	-3021.22	4	6050.44	3.35	0.13
D	-6287.15	4	12,582.31	0.00	0.85	-3019.54	4	6047.09	0.00	0.72
(b) <i>Andrena flavipes</i>										
Denmark (DK) (3389 SNPs)						Netherlands (NL) (6668 SNPs)				
A	-5262.58	3	10,531.16	6.09	0.03	-8193.79	3	16,393.59	161.97	0.00
B	-5260.36	4	10,528.71	3.64	0.11	-8115.47	4	16,238.93	7.31	0.02
C	-5258.54	4	10,525.07	0.00	0.66	-8113.91	4	16,235.81	4.19	0.11
D	-5262.40	4	10,532.81	7.74	0.01	-8111.81	4	16,231.62	0.00	0.87
Switzerland (CH) (7492 SNPs)						Spain (ES) (5623 SNPs)				
A	-8787.18	3	17,580.35	169.26	0.00	-5389.38	3	10,784.75	103.39	0.00
B	-8703.52	4	17,415.04	3.95	0.10	-5339.27	4	10,686.54	5.17	0.06
C	-8701.55	4	17,411.09	0.00	0.75	-5339.14	4	10,686.27	4.91	0.07
D	-8703.21	4	17,414.42	3.33	0.14	-5336.68	4	10,681.36	0.00	0.86

770 lnL, maximum likelihood estimate of the model; k, number of parameters in the model; AIC,
 771 Akaike's information criterion value; ΔAIC, difference in AIC value from that of the strongest
 772 model; ω_i, AIC weight.

773

774 **TABLE 3** Parameters inferred from coalescent simulations with FASTSIMCOAL2 under the most supported demographic model (Model C
775 or Model D, as indicated in Table 2) for pairs of populations of *Coccinella septempunctata* and *Andrena flavipes* sampled in agricultural
776 and nearby semi-natural landscapes from different countries. Table shows point estimates and lower and upper 95% confidence
777 intervals for each parameter, including mutation-scaled ancestral effective population sizes (ϑ_{ANC}), contemporary effective population
778 sizes for populations from natural areas (ϑ_{NAT}), timing of population split (T_{DIV} , in number of generations), and unidirectional migration
779 rates (m_{AN} or m_{NA} , depending on the most supported model; Table 2). Contemporary effective population size for populations from
780 agricultural areas (ϑ_{AGR}) was calculated from their respective levels of nucleotide diversity (π ; Table 1) and fixed in FASTSIMCOAL2
781 analyses to enable the estimation of other parameters (see the Materials and Methods section for further details). Superscripts in the
782 first column indicate the most supported model (Model C or Model D). Population codes as described in Table 1.

Code	ϑ_{ANC}		ϑ_{NAT}		T_{DIV}		$m_{\text{NA}} / m_{\text{AN}}$	
	Point	95% CI	Point	95% CI	Point	95% CI	Point	95% CI
<i>(a) Coccinella septempunctata</i>								
EE ^D	6579	5637 – 7291	24,889	19,358 – 33,796	6661	5626 – 8002	5.57×10^{-4}	$4.17 \times 10^{-4} - 7.08 \times 10^{-4}$
DK ^D	8191	6885 – 8985	82,132	67,815 – 109,399	10,385	9313 – 12,554	2.81×10^{-4}	$2.34 \times 10^{-4} - 3.41 \times 10^{-4}$
NL ^D	5519	4383 – 6360	29,795	22,444 – 40,894	7090	5913 – 8789	5.34×10^{-4}	$4.03 \times 10^{-4} - 7.31 \times 10^{-4}$
GB ^C	13077	10278 – 16,041	113,536	88,194 – 169,780	10,098	7670 – 13,554	2.35×10^{-4}	$1.95 \times 10^{-4} - 2.91 \times 10^{-4}$
HU ^D	8179	6804 – 9029	61,597	51,126 – 75,089	9830	8959 – 11,936	2.76×10^{-4}	$2.35 \times 10^{-4} - 3.12 \times 10^{-4}$
CH ^D	5419	4551 – 6369	21,203	13,913 – 30,169	4445	3927 – 5945	5.79×10^{-4}	$3.90 \times 10^{-4} - 8.21 \times 10^{-4}$
<i>(b) Andrena flavipes</i>								
DK ^C	118,487	59,169 – 126,548	51,303	20,647 – 66,866	8338	1857 – 17,100	2.27×10^{-4}	$1.67 \times 10^{-4} - 2.86 \times 10^{-4}$
NL ^D	13,751	11,544 – 14,635	39,466	31,734 – 51,439	15,015	12,642 – 18,271	4.79×10^{-4}	$3.91 \times 10^{-4} - 5.73 \times 10^{-4}$
CH ^C	18,113	13,911 – 21,774	127,634	99,263 – 170,344	12,537	10,399 – 16,085	3.74×10^{-4}	$3.04 \times 10^{-4} - 4.42 \times 10^{-4}$
ES ^D	4381	3832 – 4712	20,900	15,414 – 26,253	4847	4376 – 5551	5.67×10^{-4}	$4.46 \times 10^{-4} - 7.42 \times 10^{-4}$

783

784 **FIGURE 1** (A) Schematic illustrating the hypothesis of unidirectional gene flow from semi-natural
 785 to nearby agricultural landscapes for populations of the pest predator *Coccinella septempunctata*
 786 (shown in panel A) and the pollinator *Andrena flavipes*. Panel (B) shows the four alternative gene
 787 flow models tested using FASTSIMCOAL2. Parameters include mutation-scaled ancestral effective
 788 population sizes (ϑ_{ANC}), contemporary effective population sizes for populations from agricultural
 789 (ϑ_{AGR}) and semi-natural (ϑ_{NAT}) landscapes, timing of population split (T_{DIV}), and symmetric (m) and
 790 unidirectional (m_{AN} and m_{NA}) migration rates.

791

792

793

794 **FIGURE 2** Map showing the location of study sites in seven European countries, each including
795 an agricultural (brown dots) and a nearby semi-natural (green triangles) plot. Geographical
796 coordinates are given in Table 1 and satellite images for each sampling site are presented in
797 Figure S1.

798

799

800

801 **FIGURE 3** Results of genetic assignments based on the Bayesian method implemented in the program STRUCTURE for populations of
 802 (A) *Coccinella septempunctata* and (B) *Andrena flavipes* sampled in agricultural (agr.) and nearby semi-natural (nat.) landscapes from
 803 different countries. STRUCTURE analyses for *A. flavipes* were performed for all populations jointly (top) and excluding populations from
 804 Spain (bottom). Analyses are based on a random subset of 10,000 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). Each individual is
 805 represented by a vertical bar, which is partitioned into K colored segments showing the individual's probability of belonging to the
 806 cluster with that color. Thin vertical black lines separate individuals from different populations. Population codes as described in
 807 Table 1.

808
 809

810 **FIGURE 4** Principal component analyses (PCA) of genetic variation for populations of (A) *Coccinella septempunctata* and (B, C)
 811 *Andrena flavipes* sampled in agricultural (agr.; dots) and nearby semi-natural (nat.; triangles) landscapes from different countries.
 812 Principal component analyses for *A. flavipes* were performed for (B) all populations jointly and (C) excluding populations from Spain.
 813 Analyses are based on a random subset of 10,000 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). Population codes as described in Table 1.

